

MICROBIAL CONTAMINATION OF SOME HAWKED HERBAL PRODUCTS IN ADO-EKITI, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

An investigation was conducted on the microbial contamination of some herbal products hawked in Ado-Ekiti metropolis. Eight samples were randomly collected from herbal medicine hawkers and were subjected to bacteriological examination and phytochemical analysis. Seven bacteria namely: *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Serratia marcescens*, *Klebsiella pneumonia* and *Proteus mirabilis* were isolated from one two samples. Mean total bacterial counts ranged from 4.0×10^4 – 1.7×10^7 cfu/ml. The total counts for *E.coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ranged from 3.7×10^4 – 2.8×10^5 , 1.0×10^4 – 2.8×10^4 and 2.0×10^4 – 8.0×10^4 cfu/ml respectively. Fungal counts ranged from 3.0×10^1 and 4.0×10^4 spore forming unit per millilitres. Phytochemical analysis of the products examined revealed the occurrence of alkaloids, saponins, phenols and tannin. Overall resistance pattern by the bacterial isolates to standard antibiotics were erythromycin (100%), ampicillin (100%), penicillin (100%), clindamycin (100%), tetracycline (75%), cotrimoxazole (72%), nalidixic acid (72%), nitrofurantoin (63%) colistin (50%), gentamicin (40%) and ciprofloxacin (0%). The result of this piece of work revealed the need for adequate quality control measure to be put in place for herbal preparations for commercial purpose in order to safeguard the health of the populace especially in Nigeria.

KEYWORDS: herbal products, microbial contamination, antibiotic resistance patterns, quality control

INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, there appears to be an overwhelming increase in the public awareness and usage of herbal medical products in the treatments and or prevention of diseases (Okunola *et al.*, 2007) with this increased usage , the safety, efficacy and quality of these medicines have been an important concern for health authorities and health professionals.

Although the World Health Organization (WHO) has advocated for the integration of herbal medicinal products into the primary health care system of developing countries (WHO, 1978,1989), safety issues related to herbal drugs continue to be ignored by herbalist whose method of concocting herbal preparations for the public use are usually unhygienic leading to microbiological hazards (Esimone *et al.*, 2007).

These herbal remedies are often perceived as being natural and therefore safe, but they are not free from adverse effects, which may be due to factors such as adulteration, substitution, contamination, misidentification, lack of standardization, incorrect preparation and /or dosage, inappropriate labeling and or advertisement (Lau *et al.*, 2003). In contrast to chemically defined medical products, the biopharmaceutical quality and behaviour of herbal medicinal products are often not well documented (EMEA/HMPWP,2003) 103 (2003). The WHO Good Manufacturing Practices Guideline has provided technical guidelines to national regulatory authorities, scientific organizations, and manufacturer to undertake an assessment of the documentation/ submission/dossiers in respect of herbal medicinal products. In Nigeria, the national Agency for Food Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC) is responsible for Drug Administration and control of the quality of medicinal products including herbal medicinal products generally available in the markets. (Okunola *et al.*, 2007).

In an attempt to enhance the acceptability of the herbal medicinal products by consumers, many of the products have been formulated into conventional modern dosage forms such as tablets, capsules, suspensions, solutions and powder. Due to the prevalence of these herbal medicinal products in the markets it is of great interest to evaluate the pharmaceutical qualities of these products irrespective of the medicinal content and therapeutic claims (Okunola *et*

al., 2007). Many medicinal plants of Africa have been investigated for their chemical components and some of the isolated compounds have been shown to possess interesting biological activity.

However, this study was aimed at evaluating the microbial quality of hawked herbal products in Ado-Ekiti metropolis and to determine public health risk that such products pose to the community.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Collection of herbal samples from hawkers:

Eight samples of herbal products were randomly collected from hawkers within Ado-Ekiti metropolis (Plate 1). The samples were transferred to the laboratory in ice pebbles for microbiological analysis.

Determination of microbial loads of the herbal samples:

Exactly 10ml of each sample (10ml) was aseptically transferred into a corresponding sterile tube containing 90 ml of sterile distilled water and ten-fold serially dilution was carried out. One milliliter of dilution 10^{-4} was mixed with 15ml of sterile molten standard plate count agar or potato dextrose agar which was cooled to 45°C for bacterial and fungal respectively, and poured into Petri dishes. The plates were allowed to set and incubated at 37° C for bacterial counts, and 27° C for fungal counts.

Isolation and identification of potential pathogens in the herbal samples:

The media used were nutrient agar, MacConkey agar, Eosin methylene blue agar, Manitol salt agar and Salmonella-Shigella agar. Potato dextrose agar was used to isolate fungi. Each sample, 1ml was transferred onto the each medium and spread on the surface with glass spreader. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 72 hours. Pure cultures were obtained from the plates and stored on agar slants and kept in the refrigerator until used. The biochemical test conducted on the isolates were indole production, citrate utilization, hydrogen sulphide production, urease, catalase and oxidase test (Cowan and Steel, 2003).

Antibiotics susceptibility test

The antibiotic susceptibility tests were performed on Mueller Hinton agar plate.

The bacterial isolates from the samples were reactivated by subculturing from agar slant onto nutrient agar plate and was incubated for 18-24 hours. The inoculum was standardized by transferring three distinct and separate colonies of the pure culture of the test organism using sterile wire loop into 5mls of tryptone soy broth. The broth was incubated for 3 hours at 37°C to allow for the growth of test organism till the density was equivalent to the turbidity of 0.5 McFarland BaSO₄.

The standardized inocula were swabbed onto Mueller-Hinton agar (OXOID) plate. Antibiotics discs (OXOID) containing the following pefloxacin (5µg),

ofloxacin (5µg), ciprofloxacin (5µg), norfloxacin (10µg), amoxicillin (10µg), nalidixic acid (30µg) and nitrofurantoin (300µg), were placed on the inoculated plates and pressed firmly onto the agar complete contact. The plates were inverted and left on the work table for 30 minutes to allow for diffusion of antibiotics into the agar. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 18-24 hours. The susceptibility of each isolate to each antibiotic was shown by a clear zone of growth inhibition and this was measured using a meter rule in millimeters. The diameter of the zone of inhibition was then interpreted using standard chart (NCCLS, 2003).

Phytochemical screening of herbal product samples:

Screening for phytochemical components was conducted on each sample using the method described by Herbourne (1973) and Odebiyi and Sofowora (1978).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The total bacterial counts (TBC) of all the test herbal samples ranged from 4.0×10^4 to 1.7×10^6 cfu/ml. A total of 23 bacteria and fungi (20 bacteria and 3 fungal strains) were isolated from herbal products examined. Six (60%) of the sample were contaminated with *Escherichia coli* (3.7×10^4 – 2.8×10^5 cfu/ml) which is an intestinal bacterium and an indication of fecal contamination. Four (40%) were contaminated with *Salmonella spp* and *Pseudomonas*

aeruginosa in the range of 2.8×10^4 to 8.0×10^4 cfu/ml.. Three (30%) were contaminated with *Staphylococcus aureus* (1.0×10^4 - 2.8×10^4 cfu/ml), two (20%) were contaminated with *Serratia marcescens*, three (30%) were contaminated with *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, one (10%) contained *proteus mirabilis* (Tables 1, 2).

The bacteria isolated were sensitive to fluorquinolones (ciprofloxacin) but resistant to gentamycin, streptomycin, nalidixic acid, tetracycline, and colistin with pattern ranging from 50% to 100% (Fig 1).

The three strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated the examined herbal products were resistant to penicillin, clindamycin fusidic acid, erythromycin, trimethoprim, tetracycline and sulphamoxazole. All the gram negative rods isolated were resistant to the β -lactam antibiotics (ampicillin, and cephalotin). All the *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strains isolated were resistant to cotrimoxazole, ampicillin, cephalotin, streptomycin and sulphafriad. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains were resistant to ampicillin and cephalotin. Overall resistance pattern by the bacterial isolates were erythromycin (100%), ampicillin (100%), penicillin (100%), clindamycin (100%), tetracycline (75%), cotrimoxazole (72%), nalidixic acid (72%), nitrofurantoin (63%) colistin (50%), gentamicin (40%) and ciprofloxacin (0%) (Fig.1). All the bacterial isolates exhibited multiple antibiotic resistance pattern (Table 3). The results showed that all the eight samples of the herbal products contain alkaloids, tannins, saponins and flavonoids. An essentially herbal product usually consists of more than one plant or active constituent. Their efficacies in terms of therapeutic effect are not provided by single groups of compounds. Some of these compounds act synergistically to modify the bioavailability and efficacy of the active constituent (Okunola *et al.*, 2007). The presence of microbial contaminant in non-sterile pharmaceutical products can reduce or even inactivate the therapeutic activity of the product and has potential to adversely affect patient taking the medicines (Nakajima *et al.*, 2003). Some infectious disease outbreaks have been associated with the use of heavily contaminated raw materials of natural origin (Kallings *et al.*, 1966). Since the microbial quality of the HMPs is influenced by the environments and quality of the raw materials used during formulation, the manufacturers should ensure that the microbial load is brought to a minimal safety level in the raw materials, finished dosage forms, and the packaging components, to maintain appropriate quality, safety, and efficacy of the products.

These products were purchased by the hawkers and are being re-sold to people. Most of these products get contaminated through hand long by these local hawkers thereby reducing the effectiveness of the drug and also posing a potential health hazard to the consumers. The bacterial contaminants isolated from the test herbal preparations showed wide resistance to penicillin, ampicillin and cephalotin suggesting that they could be producers of β - lactamase. More disturbing is the resistance to trimethoprim, sulphamoxazole and cotrimoxazole observed especially against gram negative isolates.

Escherichia coli were the most frequently isolated species in these medications which is an intestinal bacterium and an indicator of faecal contaminant. Presence of *Escherichia coli* in the sample indicates poor hygiene practices and lack of adequate handling of the products. According to the European pharmacopoeia 2007, no *Salmonella sp* or *Escherichia coli* strain should be present in the samples. The *Escherichia coli* isolate shows a wide resistance to ampicillin, cephalotin, cotrimoxazole sulphafriad and tetracycline. The *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated showed wide resistance to penicillin suggesting possibly that they are producers of penicillinase. Resistance to trimethoprim by *Staphylococcus aureus* has been reported with increasing frequency (Archer *et al.*, 1986). Studies of clinical strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* have often reported multi-drug resistance in the microorganism. *Staphylococcus aureus* can originate from handlers and it is a normal flora of the human skin.

The number of bacterial and fungal strains capable of causing infections is increasing, and many of them are resistance to one or more of the antimicrobial agents used in its therapy. This problem has risen to a serious public health concern with economic, social and political implication that are global in scope and across all environmental and ethnic boundaries (Esimone *et al.*, 2007). The high rate of resistance to antimicrobial agent by strains isolated from these herbal preparations may indicate a widespread of antibiotic resistance among microorganisms from different sources (Esimone *et al.*, 2007).

In conclusion, there is need for constant monitoring and control of quality of the herbal medicinal products manufactured, sold, advertised, and used in Nigeria by appropriate agencies. There should be an adequate standard

and specification for the HMPs being sold to the public .Hawkers of herbal medicinal products also contributes immensely to the poor quality of the products, due to their poor and hygienic practices.

Hawking of herbal medicines should be dissuaded and only thoroughly monitored herbal products (i.e. those who's microbiological, phytochemical, and physiochemical qualities are government or NAFDAC approved should be allowed for sale to the public.

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Table 1: Detection of pathogenic bacteria and fungi in hawked herbal products

Microorganisms	Detection of bacteria and fungi						
	AMH	PLC	CTC	OMT	COV	YOB	ATC
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	+	+	+	-	-	+	-
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Proteus morabilis</i>	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	-	+	-	-	-	+	-
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	+	+	-	+	+	-	-
<i>Serratia marscens</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-	+
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	-	-	+	+	-	-	-
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	+	-	-	+	-	-	-

Antimalarial herbal products (AMH), Pile concoction (PLC), Coated tongue concoction (CTC), Oroki herbal mixture (OMT), Convulsion herbal mixture (COV), Blood circulation herbal mixture(YOB) and Antityphoid herbal mixture (ATC). (+) indicates positive in the herbal products, (-) indicate negative in the herbal products

Table 2: Bacterial and fungal population of herbal products

Herbal products	Microbial counts (cfu/ml)					
	TBC	EC	ST	SA	PS	Fungal counts
Pile concoction	17x10 ⁶	2.8x10 ⁵	2.8x10 ⁴	0	7.0x10 ⁴	3.0x10 ¹
Antimalarial herbal mixture	7.2x10 ⁴	3.7x10 ⁴	0	0	8.0x10 ⁴	4.0x10 ⁵
Coated tongue concoction	8.5x10 ⁵	2.0x10 ⁵	0	1.0x10 ⁴	0	0
Oroki herbal mixture	7.2x.10 ⁵	0	0	2.8x10 ⁴	0	1.2x10 ⁴
Convulsion herbal mixture	3.8x10 ⁵	0	0	2.3x10 ⁴	2.0x10 ⁴	0
Blood circulation Herbal products	2.8x10 ⁵	1.8x10 ⁵	0	0	0	0
Antityphoidal herbal mixture	4.0x10 ⁴	0	0	0	0	0

Total bacterial counts (TBC), *Escherichia coli* (EC), *Salmonella typhi* (ST), *Staphylococcus aureus* (SA), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (PS) and Fungal counts (FGC)

Fig.1 : Overall antibiotic resistance pattern of bacterial isolate from hawked herbal products

Table 3: Antibiotic resistance profile of bacterial isolate from herbal products

Bacterial isolates	Isolate code	Multiple antibiotic resistotypes	No of antibiotics
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	PS01	AMP/COT/STR/CLT/STD	5
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	PS02	AMP/COT/STR/TET/CLT/STD	6
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	PS03	AMP/COT/GEN/NAL/NIT/COL/STR/TET	8
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	PS04	AMP/COT/GEN/NAL/NIT/COL/STR/TET	8
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	EC01	AMP/COT/STR/TET/CLT/STD	6
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	EC02	AMP/COT/TET/CLT/STD	5
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	EC03	AMP/COT/NAL/NIT/STR/CLT/STD	7
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	EC04	AMP/COT/GEN/NAL/NIT/COL/STR/TET	8
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	EC05	AMP/COT/GEN/STR/TET/CLT/STD	7
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	EC06	AMP/COT/GEN/COL/TET	5
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	KL01	AMP/COT/NIT/STR	4
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	KL02	AMP/COL/CLT/STD	4
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	KL03	AMP/NIT/CLT/STD	4
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	ST01	TET/PEN/CLN/FUS/ERY/TRM	7
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	ST02	TET/PEN/FUS/ERY/TRM/CLN	6
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	ST03	TET/PEN/FUS/ERY/TRM/CLN	6
<i>Serratia marscens</i>	SM01	AMP/COL/STR/TET/CLT/STD	6
<i>Serratia marscens</i>	SM02	AMP/GEN/NAL/COL/TET	5
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	SS01	AMP/GEN/COL/TET	4
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	PM01	AMP/COT/NAL/NIT/STR	5

Table 3: Phytochemical constituents of the herbal products.

Herbal product samples	Phenols	Alkaloids	Flavonoids	Saponins
Antimalarial herbal mixture	+	-	-	-
Pile concoction(A)	+	+	+	+
Pile concoction (B)	+	-	-	+
Oroki herbal mixture	-	+	+	+
Convulsion herbal mixture	+	-	-	+
Blood circulation herbal mixture	+	+	+	+
Antityphoidal herbal mixture	+	-	-	+
Coated tongue concoction	+	-	-	+

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